

Making Sustainability Certification Work in Contexts of Informality and Governance Risks: Evidence from Ecuador's Cacao and Flower Sectors

DOI10.5281/zenodo.20770581

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Key Messages

1. Sustainability certifications such as Fairtrade can improve market access and promote sustainable production but benefits often fail to reach the most marginalized producers.
2. Evidence from Ecuador's cacao and flower sectors shows that complex certification requirements favor producers with existing financial, organizational, and administrative capacity.
3. Smallholders face barriers linked to compliance costs, weak cooperatives, training needs, and traceability requirements, limiting participation in certified markets.
4. The formalization and bureaucratic complexity of certification can create openings for informal practices and corruption risks, reinforcing rural inequalities if unaddressed.
5. Policy action is needed to strengthen producer organizations, expand technical assistance, and adapt standards to local contexts.

Context & Purpose

Sustainability certifications such as Fairtrade are widely promoted to improve market access and livelihoods for small-scale producers in the Global South. Yet evidence from Ecuador's cacao and flower sectors reveals a persistent gap between policy objectives and implementation outcomes. Complex administrative and certification requirements can be difficult for producers to meet, encouraging informal practices and [weakening](#) oversight. While designed to support marginalized producers, certification requirements often generate structural barriers that limit participation. This brief draws on these two sectors to assess how certification operates in practice and identify policy options to improve inclusiveness and effectiveness.

Insights & Findings

- Certification systems tend to benefit better-organized and better-resourced producers rather than the most vulnerable [farmers](#).
- In cacao production, certification requires substantial investment in training, traceability systems, record-keeping, and cooperative management, meaning only stronger cooperatives can consistently comply.
- Weak or informal producer groups face exclusion, high administrative burdens, and limited returns even when they are included in certification schemes.
- In the flower sector, barriers are even more pronounced, with many small- and medium-scale producers effectively excluded due to a lack of tailored certification pathways

Across both sectors, the emphasis on credibility and market trust leads to strict entry requirements that unintentionally reproduce existing inequalities

- The formalization and bureaucratic complexity of certification can create spaces for circumvention,

including informal practices and the manipulation of compliance and verification [processes](#).

Source: Author's personal collection, cacao seedling planting process. Ecuador.

Policy Relevance

- Current certification frameworks risk reinforcing structural inequality by excluding the very producers they aim to support.
- The effectiveness of certification depends not only on standard-setting but also on producers' institutional and organizational capacity.
- Without complementary public support, certification is insufficient to achieve both inclusive rural development and equitable market integration.
- A gap persists between sustainability objectives (inclusion) and implementation realities (selective participation based on capacity).

Recommendations

- Targeted capacity-building: Governments and local authorities should provide training, technical assistance, and administrative support to help smallholders meet certification requirements, since certification bodies often face conflicts of interest in providing direct support.
- Strengthen cooperatives: Invest in governance, financial management, and organizational capacity to improve collective access to certification.
- Context-sensitive standards: Develop hierarchical or adapted certification schemes that better reflect the realities of small- and medium-scale producers, especially in floriculture.
- Policy integration: Combine certification schemes with broader rural development programs to avoid placing sustainability compliance burdens solely on producers.

Contact and Attribution

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This brief is based on research conducted in 2025 from COST Action CA21133 – GLITSS (Globalization, Illicit Trade, Sustainability and Security), supported by COST and MSCA Presilient (Post-pandemic Resilient Communities), ID 101073394.